

1Research Article

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3EFFECT OF TELECONNECTION BETWEEN INDIAN SUMMER MONSOON & IOD ON UPPER BLUE NILE BASIN, 4ETHIOPIA USING WAVELET TECHNIQUES

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11Abstract

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13Most of the Ethiopian annual rainfall is contributed by Upper Blue Nile Basin (UBNB) and it plays an important role in agriculture
14and consequently economy of the country. In this study we applied various wavelet analysis methods (CWT, WTC & PWC) to
15explore the influence of Ocean-atmospheric circulation pattern such as ENSO, IOD and Indian summer monsoon (ISM) on the
16variability of precipitation over the UBNB using 20 Rain gauge stations for the last 32 years (1987-2018). The wavelet analysis on
17precipitation reveals a dominant oscillation of 8-16 months for all stations over UBNB. The wavelet transform coherence (WTC)
18analysis indicates ENSO is a dominant driving factor for precipitation variability across the UBNB with the effective periodicity of 8-
1916 months, while IOD at 4-8 months. Further the analysis of summer precipitation and ISMI implies a significant contribution of
20Indian monsoon to the variability of summer precipitation over the basin at 4-6 months periodicity via the modulation of ENSO and
21IOD. The spatial pattern of precipitation during ENSO and IOD events leads to the conclusion that the co-existing of El Niño and
22nIOD is associated with deficit rainfall while the La Niña and pIOD events leads to excess rainfall over the basin.

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24 **Keywords** Precipitation . Teleconnection . ENSO . IOD . ISMI . Wavelet Transform . Upper Blue Nile

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27 1. Introduction

28 Hydroclimates like precipitation are related to large-scale atmospheric variables via ocean-atmospheric circulations. Such
29 circulation patterns are connected to changes in climatic conditions due to factors like population and technology growth,
30 urbanization and economic development. Precipitation variability affects water resources sustainability which includes the
31 availability, management, and utilization of water resources. This, in turn, may affect ecosystems, land productivity, agriculture,
32 food security, water quantity and human health [1]. Variability in precipitation at the basin scale can cause social and economic
33 problems, especially in developing countries like Ethiopia, because their economy is dependent upon the rain-fed agriculture [2].

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35 The Ethiopian precipitation is significantly influenced by several large scale atmospheric patterns, such as the El Niño
36 Southern Oscillation (ENSO), the Pacific-North American (PNA) pattern, the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), the Pacific
37 Decadal Oscillation (PDO) as well as other teleconnection patterns as reported by different researchers [3-9].

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39 ENSO has been a subject of intense research over the last three decades, to the extent that SST anomalies in the tropical
40 Pacific are primarily used as main predictors in forecasting Ethiopian rainfall by National Meteorology Agency (NMA) [6].
41 *Abteu et al.* [7] evaluated the relationship between ENSO indices and the Blue Nile River Basin hydrology, based on the
42 correlation analysis, they concluded that high rainfall and high flows are likely to occur during La Niña years and dry years are
43 likely to occur during El Niño years. Extreme dry and wet years are very likely to occur correspond with ENSO events. The great
44 Ethiopian famine of 1888-1892 corresponds to one of the strongest El Niño years.

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46 The IOD had traditionally been viewed as an artifact of the ENSO system although increasingly the evidence is revealing that
47 it is separate and distinct phenomenon. The influence of the IOD is not just confined to the tropical region, but reaching far to the
48 whole globe [10]. The evidence indicates Indian Ocean SST anomalies have a significant impact on regional atmospheric
49 circulation and rainfall anomalies that extend into south eastern Africa [11].

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51 Teleconnection between large-scale oceanic-atmospheric circulation patterns and the variability of precipitation has been a
52 research topic of increasing interest. Generally, tele connection studies uses simple regression analysis and correlation measure
53 (e.g. Pearson's correlation), rather than coherence and interdependence among parameters, however some of large scale
54 circulation patterns are essentially interdependent. In this study, we performed wavelet coherence analysis to study the relation
55 between Z and X would inherently considers the effect of Y. Hence, it is important
56 to study the standalone effect of every climate index on precipitation separately, in order to better understanding of
57 meteorological connections with large-scale climatic oscillation patterns. Better understanding of spatially and temporally
58 organized links between precipitation variability patterns and ocean-atmosphere at large scales would be a considerable asset.
59 Anticipating regional predisposition to rainfall variability in a particular phase of oscillation in the atmosphere-ocean system
60 could help in improving preparedness to emergency [12].

61
62 It is indispensable to study the spatio-temporal characteristics of large-scale climatic factors with the precipitation variability
63 for effective management and allocation of water resources[13]. Hence forth our study focus on the effect of large scale ocean-
64 atmospheric circulation pattern such as ENSO, IOD and ISMI on the precipitation variability of UBNB in Ethiopia. This study
65 will help the water resources management agencies of Ethiopia to mitigate the potential impacts of droughts and floods.

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68 2. Data Source and Methodology

69 2.1. Study area description

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71 The Upper Blue Nile Basin is the largest tributary of the River Nile with a drainage area about 1,76,000 km² covering 17% of
72 Ethiopia. Its head waters start from Lake Tana at an elevation of 1800 m above sea level at Bahir Dar. The basin is located in the
73 northwestern part of Ethiopia between longitudes of 34°30' - 39°45' E and latitudes of 7°45' - 12°45' N, as shown in Fig. 1. The
74 basin topography is composed of hills and highlands in the northeastern part, and valleys continue in the southern and western
75 parts [14]. One of the high water surplus areas in Ethiopia is the UBNB catchment [15]. The upper part of Blue Nile records
76 rainfall almost all year round in varying amounts with high rainfall between June-September season. The mean annual rainfall in
77 the basin ranges from 800 to 2200 mm. Agriculture is a major livelihood source for the population living within the basin,
78 sustaining tens of millions of people.

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Fig. 1. The geographical location of the Upper Blue Nile Basin (UBNB) and ground rainfall stations selected for this study.

2.2. Data Source

In this study we utilized monthly rainfall data obtained from National Meteorological Agency (NMA) of Ethiopia over 20 selected gauge stations within Upper Blue Nile Basin during the period of 1987-2018. The annual rainfall data is obtained from the monthly data for of those stations. The missing data points have been filled by spline interpolation procedure. Station selection is based on the availability of gauge data and their relative locations in the basin. We classified the entire UBNB basin into 5 regions (Northern, Eastern Southern, Western and Central) based on selected stations pertaining the availability of gauge station data and their relative locations (Table 1). In addition to gauge data, the Climate Hazards group Infrared Precipitation with Stations (CHIRPS) monthly data is also used for the spatial analysis. The data can freely access through the web: <https://www.chc.ucsb.edu/data/chirps>.

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Table 1: Classification and general identification of the selected gauge stations over the Upper Blue Nile Basin.

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Study Regions	Rainfall Stations	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation (m)
Northern	Debre Tabor	11.86	37.99	2612
	Gondar	12.52	37.43	1973
	Debark	13.14	37.90	2836
	Metema	12.77	36.41	790
Eastern	Debre Berhan	9.63	39.50	2750
	Combolcha	11.08	39.71	1857
	Alem Ketema	10.06	38.99	2204
	Mehal Meda	10.31	39.66	3084
Southern	Addis Ababa	8.98	38.80	2354
	Jimma	7.67	36.82	1710
	Nekemte	9.08	36.54	2119
	Bedele	8.45	36.35	2000
Western	Asossa	10.00	34.51	1600
	Pawe	11.31	36.41	1119
	Nedjo	9.52	35.49	1877
Central	Bahir Dar	11.60	37.38	1800
	Dangila	11.43	36.84	2116
	Enjibara	10.99	36.91	2568
	Debre Werk	10.65	38.16	2508
	Debre Markos	10.33	37.73	2446

150Intensity of the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) is represented by anomalous SST gradient between the western equatorial Indian Ocean
151(50°E-70°E and 10°S-10°N) and the south eastern equatorial Indian Ocean (90°E-110°E and 10°S-0°N). This gradient is named as
152Dipole Mode Index (DMI). When the DMI is positive then, the phenomenon is referred as the positive IOD (pIOD) and when it is
153negative, it is referred as negative IOD (nIOD). In order to explore the teleconnection between the precipitation over UBNB with
154Indian ocean, The DMI data is obtained from the website of the Climate Prediction Centre of National Oceanic and Atmospheric
155Administration (NOAA-CPC): https://psl.noaa.gov/gcos_wgsp/Timeseries/DMI/. The data within the time range 1987-2018 has been
156considered in this study. There are several indices used to monitor the tropical Pacific, all of which are based on SST anomalies
157averaged across a given region. For this study monthly SST anomaly data over Niño4 region (5°N 5°S, 160°E-15°W) was obtained

158from the website <https://psl.noaa.gov/data/timeseries/monthly/NINO4/>. The Niño4 index captures SST anomalies in the central
159equatorial Pacific. This region tends to have less variance than the other Niño regions. The monthly means of Indian Summer
160Monsoon Index (ISMI) data is available from the Monsoon Monitoring Page maintained by the University of Hawaii from
161<http://apdrc.soest.hawaii.edu/projects/monsoon/>. The monthly indices from 1987 - 2018 were accessed for this study.

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164 2.3. Methodology

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166 2.3.1. The rainfall anomaly index (RAI)

167The RAI was developed and first used by Van Rooy [16] to assign magnitudes to positive and negative precipitation anomalies. RAI
168enables to monitor dry and wet periods and their alternations according to positive (wet) and negative (dry) values. From the
169precipitation data, the RAI can be calculated using the following equations:

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$$171 \quad RAI = 3 \left[\frac{N - \dot{N}}{\dot{M} - \dot{N}} \right], \text{ For positive anomalies} \quad (1)$$

$$172 \quad RAI = -3 \left[\frac{N - \dot{N}}{\dot{X} - \dot{N}} \right], \text{ For negative anomalies} \quad (2)$$

173Where

174 N = current monthly/yearly rainfall;

175 \dot{N} = monthly/yearly average rainfall of the historical series (mm);

176 \dot{M} = average of the ten highest monthly/yearly precipitations of the historical series (mm);

177 \dot{X} = average of the ten lowest monthly/yearly precipitations of the historical series (mm); and positive anomalies have their values
178above average and negative anomalies have their values below average.

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180 2.3.2. Continuous wavelet transform (CWT)

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182Various methods have been introduced for signal processing and time series analysis. Most of these methods are mathematical
183transforms that convert vectors or functions from one space to another. Some of the transformations (e.g. Fourier transforms) are only
184appropriate for the analysis of stationary time series exhibiting a uniform oscillation pattern over time. These transformations are not
185robust enough for the analysis of non-stationary time series, since they cannot identify all frequencies within the time series [17,18].

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187 Wavelet transform is a powerful and accurate mathematical transformation, widely used for signal processing and time series
188analysis. The theory behind wavelet transform is relatively similar to that of Fourier transforms, but offers much greater flexibility
189allowing a highly accurate capture of all frequencies present in a given time series [17,19]. CWT is recognized as one of the robust
190tools for the investigation of processes with high temporal variability [20]. It is appropriate in particular for examining non-stationary
191processes, like climate variables. The CWT of the signal $x(t)$ generating a wavelet spectrum is expressed as Eq. (1)

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$$W(s, \tau) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{s}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \psi^* \left(\frac{t-\tau}{s} \right) dt \quad (1)$$

193 Every wavelet length is finite and ever precisely localized in time. The mother wavelet includes two parameters: scaling s and
194 temporal location τ .

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$$\psi_{s,\tau}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{s}} \psi \left(\frac{t-\tau}{s} \right)$$

196 With

197 $\psi_{s,\tau}(t)$: Wavelet daughter;198 s : scale parameter;199 τ : time-localization parameter;

200 ψ and ψ^* represent the wavelet function and complex conjugate, respectively. With $\tau=0$ and $s=1$ denotes the basic or mother
201 wavelet. The flexibility in the wavelet transform comes due to the variations in the scale, which enable to capture the long and short
202 frequency in the time series. Parameterization of scale and wavelet daughters admits the finding of various frequencies that compose
203 signal. The Morlet wavelet allows to separate the phase and amplitude of any time series and is localized in scale, which helps in
204 achieving high resolution in frequency [21-23].-

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206 2.3.2.1. Wavelet coherence transforms (WTC)

207 The wavelet coherence transform (WTC) determines the relationship between two time series by finding regions where the two time
208 series co-vary in time frequency space which may not necessarily have high power. For this reason, the WTC is necessary to analyze
209 the relationships between two processes in time-frequency space. From [Torrence and Compo \[24\]](#) the WTC of two time series is
210 defined as:

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$$R_n^2(s) = \frac{\mathcal{I} \left(s^{-1} W_n^{XY}(s) \right) \mathcal{I}^2}{S \left(s^{-1} \vee S \left(W_n^X(s) \right) \mathcal{I}^2 \right) \cdot S \left(s^{-1} \vee S \left(W_n^Y(s) \right) \mathcal{I}^2 \right)} \quad (3)$$

213 Where S is the smoothing operator defined by the wavelet type used and the entire expression is similar to that of a traditional
214 correlation coefficient localized in time-frequency space [22].

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216 2.3.2.2. Partial wavelet coherence (PWC)

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218The PWC analysis is appropriate for finding the standalone correlation between response variable y and predictor variable x_1 after
219eliminating the influence of the predictor variable x_2 , which is technically similar to the partial correlation, ranging from 0 to 1. It can
220be defined as Ng and Chan [25]

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$$RP_{y, x_1, x_2}^2(s, t) = \dots \dots \dots \quad (4)$$

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224Where R denotes the wavelet coherence between the two variables. The series x_2 shows no significantly influence on the series y if it
225is close to zero at a certain time-frequency point. A high value of partial coherence for series x_1 implies that important covariance
226exists between x_1 and y during that interval at a given period. $RP_{y, x_1, x_2}^2(s, t)$ and $RP_{y, x_2, x_1}^2(s, t)$ have significant bands, meaning
227both two series significantly influence on series y .

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231 3. Results and discussion

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233 3.1. Rainfall anomaly index (RAI)

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235Precipitation is the result of several atmospheric systems (such as topography and ITCZ) that behave at various scales and periodicity.
236Further, the irregularity and seasonality exhibited by rainfall, can be assessed by means of the climatic index. Rainfall Anomaly Index
237(RAI), developed by Van Rooy [16], is used to classify the positive and negative severities in rainfall anomalies. The Annual RAI was
238calculated by the method given in the methodology section and used to analyze the dry and rainy years. Positive RAI values represent
239rainy or wet years and the negative values represent the dry years, with different degrees of intensity as given in (Table 2).

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244 Table 2: Classification of Rainfall Anomaly Index Intensity.

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RAI range	Classification
Above 4	Extremely humid
2 to 4	Very humid
0 to 2	Humid
-2 to 0	Dry
-4 to -2	Very dry
Below -4	Extremely dry

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256 Fig. 2 (a) depicts the RAI for Northern regions of the UBNB. We can observe that 1988 and 2000 were extremely dry years with the
 257 RAI values of -4.68 and -4.35. While extremely wet years were observed during 2009 and 2015, with RAI of 4.10 and 5.12,
 258 respectively. Fig. 2 (b) indicates RAI for Eastern basin. The result shows that there were more dry years (19 years with the RAI -ve
 259 values) than rainy ones (13 years with RAI +ve values). The years of 1987, 1991 and 2015 were extremely dry with the RAI values of
 260 -5.33, -4.09 and -5.56, respectively. On the other hand, extreme humid years were observed during 2017 and 2018 with RAI values of
 261 15.15 and 10.18, respectively.

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283 Fig. 2 (a-e). Rainfall Anomaly Index for the five locations over Upper Blue Nile Basin.

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RAI

286 for Southern UBNB is shown in Fig. 2 (c). It is clearly shown that there were more dry years (19 years with a negative RAI) than wet
 287 years (13 years with positive RAI). The extreme dry years were 2002, 2003 and 2018 with the RAI of -5.63, -5.45 and -4.17,
 288 respectively. While the years 1998 and 2006 were extremely humid with RAI of 5.0 and 4.64, respectively. [Viste et al. \[26\]](#) studied the
 289 precipitation tendencies in Ethiopia and found similar results. For the Western regions of the UBNB (Fig. 2 (d)), equivalent dry and
 290 rainy years have been observed however 1996 was the year with the highest negative value (extreme dry), with a RAI of -5.56 and
 291 2014 was extreme humid with RAI of 10.91. Fig. 2 (e) indicates the RAI for Central UBNB. We can clearly observe that there were
 292 equivalent dry and rainy years. Moreover, we can observe extreme dry periods with RAI values of -4.24 and -4.83 during 1994 and
 293 1995, respectively. While extreme humid periods were during 2000 and 2006 with the RAI of 4.72 and 5.08, respectively.

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Fig. 3 (a-e). Continuous wavelet (CWT) power spectrum and global wavelet power spectrum (GWS) of precipitation time series of the five locations over UBNB.

324 3.2. Wavelet analysis
325 3.2.1. Continuous wavelet transform (CWT) analysis
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327 To understand the precipitation variability and to identify the modes of oscillation, we applied the continuous wavelet transform
 328 (CWT) technique on monthly precipitation data of 32 years (1987-2018) over 5 selected regions of UBNB (Northern, Eastern,
 329 Southern, Western and Central) and the results are displayed in Fig. 3 (a-e). We clearly identified a single dominant oscillation with
 330 periodicity of 8-16 months (or 0.7-1.3) in all 5 regions. By applying the CWT technique on 32 years (1987-2018) monthly mean
 331 values of Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) index (shown in Fig. 4 (a)) reveals a dominant long term oscillation of 16-48 months (1.3-4
 332 years) during the period of 1990-2002 and again from 2015-2018 with the periodicity of 16-28 months (1.3-2.3 years). The application
 333 of CWT on El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) index value also indicates a dominant long term oscillation of 16-64 months (2.3-
 334 5.3 years) during 1992-2002 and again from 2005-2017 as displayed in Fig. 4 (b). Along with the CWT, the features of global wavelet
 335 spectrum (GWS) for precipitation, IOD and ENSO are also presented.

Fig. 4. Continuous wavelet (CWT) spectrum and GWS of IOD (a) and Niño4 (b).

336 3.2.2. Wavelet coherence analysis (WCA)

337 3.2.2.1. Monthly precipitation and ENSO

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339 The wavelet coherence analysis (WCA) is used to statistically estimate the linkage between precipitation and the selected climate
 340 indices. The wavelet coherence between monthly precipitation over 5 regions of the UBNB and
 341 ENSO is presented in Fig. 5 (a-e). The phase differences between precipitation and climate indices can be shown by the arrows. The
 342 arrows pointing to the right (left) mean that two series are in-phase (anti-phase), while arrows pointing up (down) mean that one series
 343 leads (lags) the other by 90° .

344 It is observed from the Fig. 5 (a-e) that the influence of ENSO on the monthly precipitation clearly shows high coherence structure
 345 over all the 5 regions of UBNB with different periodicities during the study periods. A strong inter-annual to decadal-scale coherence
 346 with periodicity of 64-96 months (5.3-8 years) is observed over Northern and eastern regions of the basin ~~only~~ during the period of
 347 1994-2010. A strong but intermittency coherence on time-scales of less than 1.0 year is also noticed over all the regions of the basin
 348 during different time periods. Over all, the most important coherences between precipitation and Niño4 are observed during 1991-
 349 1994, 1999-2002 and 2005-2009 with the periodicity of 8-16 months (0.7-1.3 years), which is exactly the same (common) periodicity

350with the precipitation (as seen in Fig. 3 (a-e)) over all regions of the basin. It is also observed that these time periods were matching
351with the ENSO incident years.

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Fig. 5 (a-e). Wavelet coherence (WTC) between precipitation over UBNB and Niño4.

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3.2.2.2. Monthly precipitation and IOD

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384The coherence between precipitations over 5 regions of UBNB with IOD (Fig. 6 (a-e)) shows a large scale periodicity of 64 months
385(5.3 years) in Southern part (1992-2012) and Central part (1992-1997) of UBNB. In addition to large scale oscillations there exist
386dominant intermittent coherence with periodicity of 4-8 months (0.3- 0.6 years) is visible in all regions throughout the year. In the case
387of Central regions, the high coherence is recorded on 32 -48 months (i.e., 2.6-4 years). Finally, it is concluded that significant but
388intermittent coherences between precipitation and IOD at 4-8 months scale becomes the important and common coherence modes.

389 Our results clearly indicates the spatial and temporal variability between precipitation over UBNB and the climate indices. The
390obtained results from the WTC analysis suggest that precipitation is related to climate indices (Niño4 and IOD), but at different scales

391and at varying degrees. However, it should be noted that there is a significant level of interdependence among the climate indices.
 392Thus, for better understanding of the dynamics of the influence of the climate indices on precipitation, it is also necessary to
 393understand the standalone effect of the indices on the extreme precipitation. To this end, we perform the partial wavelet coherence
 394(PWC) analysis, and the results are presented in the next section.

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Fig. 6. Wavelet coherence (WTC) between precipitation over UBNN and IOD.

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424 **3.2.3. Partial wavelet coherence (PWC) analysis**

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426In the above results of coherence analysis the common interaction between IOD and ENSO (Niño4) has not been eliminated. Now in
 427this section we are going to eliminate the effect of IOD and investigate only the coherence between precipitation and Niño4. This
 428helps to examine the standalone effect of Niño4 over the 5 regions of UBNN precipitation. Fig. 7 (a-e) depicts the results of partial
 429wavelet coherence (PWC) analysis for 5 regions over UBNN after removing the effect of IOD. When we compare this result with the
 430results of WTC shown in Fig. 5 (a-e), the high power regions in PWC is reduced significantly because of the removal of potential
 431influence of IOD. The most important coherence modes between precipitation over the 5 regions and Niño4 indicates a dominant

432 periodicity of 8-16 months (0.6-1.3 years) time scale during 1991-1994, 1999-2002 and 2005-2009 which is present in WTC Fig. 5 (a-
 433 e), are also observed in PWC Fig. 7 (a-e) with some reductions in power, hence we conclude that the variability of precipitation over
 434 the basin during these periods is due to ENSO incidence. Moreover, in the case of Southern and Western parts of UBNB, a large scale
 435 periodicity of 32-40 months (2.6-3.3 years) (which is present in WTC analysis of ENSO (Fig. 5) (a & d)) is eliminated, which assumes
 436 to be the influence of IOD. Such reductions of the coherence modes over different regions of the basin indicates IOD has significant
 437 contribution to the relationship between precipitation and Niño4 which shows that the variability of precipitation over most parts of
 438 UBNB is triggered by IOD via the influence of ENSO. It is also supported by previous section that high RAI values from Fig. 2 (a-e)
 439 indicating extreme humid and dry years over all basin.

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Fig. 7. Partial wavelet coherence (PWC) spectra analysis between precipitation over UBNB and Niño4 after removal of the influence of IOD.

469 Similarly, Fig. 8 (a-e) shows the PWC between IOD and precipitation over the different regions of UBNB after removing the
 470 influence of Niño4. Although the change is not significant, there is some reduction in the coherence modes after removal of Niño4. As

471an example, comparing these two situations over the Southern regions of the basin (Fig. 6 (c) and Fig. 8 (c)), no noticeable change in
 472the coherence modes between the extreme precipitation and IOD is detected. These results imply that Niño4 and IOD operate at
 473distinct modes and influence of IOD are independent of ENSO events. Ultimately, it is confirmed that 4-8 months time-scale
 474coherence modes are due to the occurrence of IOD. Moreover the existence of extreme humid and dry years over Northern and
 475Eastern regions of the basin observed from the high RAI values (positive or negative) in Fig. 2 (a) & (b) during 1987-1991 and 2012
 4762018 also confirms the result, most of these periods were the of IOD occurrence periods (as shown in Table 3).

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Fig. 8. Partial wavelet coherence (PWC) spectra analysis between precipitation over UBNN and IOD after removal of the influence of Niño4.

507 3.2.4. The effect of ISMI on summer precipitation over Upper Blue Nile basin

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509 The Indian Summer Monsoon is the largest monsoon system that brings a large portion of moisture in the form of precipitation to
 510 UBNB. To investigate the relationship and coherence between summer (June-September) precipitation and the Indian Summer
 511 Monsoon Index (ISMI), we performed continuous wavelet (CWT) analysis on both ISMI and monthly summer precipitation data for
 512 32 years (1987-2018) over the 5 regions of the UBNB basin. The results are illustrated in Fig. 9 (a-f). It clearly reveals an oscillation
 513 of 2-6 months at Northern, Eastern and Central regions of the UBNB and summer precipitation during all the study periods. Further,
 514 the Southern and Western basin show same oscillations at 2-6 months during 1992-2000 and 2005-2015 and with a periodicity of 8-12
 515 months during 1995-2000. The summer precipitation shows a significant oscillation during 2004-2015 at 2-6 months time-scale. Fig.
 516 10 (a-e) presents the results of WTC analysis between summer precipitation over the 5 regions of the basin and ISMI. It is shown that
 517 the ISMI is responsible for the precipitation variability over the UBNB at 2-6 months time-scale.

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Fig. 9. Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT) power spectrum and GWS of summer (June-September) precipitation over UBNB (a-e) and ISMI time series (f).

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Fig. 10. Wavelet coherence (WTC) between summer precipitation over UBNB and ISMI.

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3.3. Spatial patterns of precipitation over UBNB

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Due to the variation of moisture flow during different Oceanic-atmospheric phases, precipitation over the UBNB also show spatial variation. In order to show the spatial pattern of summer precipitation during different phases, we identified IOD and ENSO years which could occurred simultaneously during study period (1987-2018) (Table 3).

The spatial variation of summer precipitation over the basin are caused by the northward migration of the ITCZ. Fig. 11 depicts the spatial variation of monthly summer precipitation over the entire basin during incidences of IOD and ENSO. The results showed that most parts of the basin receives maximum rainfall during La Niña and positive IOD (pIOD) (Fig. 11, top right and bottom left

587respectively), while minimal rainfall occurred during El Niño and negative IOD (nIOD) years. Though most parts of the basin receive
 588significant amount of rainfall during pIOD years, the Western and Northwest parts receive less rainfall pattern. When La Niña and
 589pIOD events occurred simultaneously (Fig. 12, bottom right), surplus rainfall is widespread and covers the entire basin and the Eastern
 590part receive significant amount of rainfall during those events.

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Table 3: List of ENSO and IOD years during 1987-2018.

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	Positive IOD	Neutral	Negative IOD
El Niño	1994, 1997, 2006, 2015, 2018	1987, 1991, 2002, 2007, 2009	1993, 2014, 2016
Neutral	2012	1990, 1995, 2001, 2003, 2004, 2005	1992, 1996, 2013
La Niña	2007, 2011	1988, 1999, 2000, 2008	1989, 1998, 2010

Fig. 11. Spatial plots showing the average summer precipitation patterns over UBNB during independent IOD and ENSO events.

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625shows the LaNiña and pIOD intensifies the Southwest monsoon and leads to high moisture transport into the basin. It is also observed
 626that the Pacific Ocean and Indian Ocean contribute intense moisture in to the UBNB during the La Niña and pIOD phases. In addition,

627the Northern and Western parts also receive modest amount of rainfall during these periods. Furthermore, when a pIOD event
 628simultaneously occurs with El Niño, the anomalous divergence center moves into the eastern tropical Indian Ocean. The anomalous
 629divergent flow, crossing the equator, converges over the Indian monsoon region, and thus cancels the ENSO induced subsidence and
 630the related deficit of rainfall. In other events, the entire basin had been affected by severe drought during the co-occurring of El Niño
 631and nIOD years (Fig. 12, bottom left). The results also reveal that the ENSO phases have more dominant effect than IOD on the
 632variability of summer precipitation. This result supports the previous studies [8, 27-29]. Moreover the studies on influence of IOD on
 633Indian summer monsoon by Ashok et al. [30] demonstrated that the positive (negative) phase of the IOD strengthens (weakens) the
 634Southwest monsoon, and causes surplus (deficit) rainfall, which clearly in agreement with our study results.

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Fig. 12. Spatial plots showing the average summer precipitation patterns over the UBNB during co-occurring IOD-ENSO events.

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659 4. Conclusion

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661This study explored the influence of large-scale Ocean-atmospheric circulation pattern such as ENSO, IOD and Indian summer
 662monsoon (ISM) on the variability of precipitation over the Upper Blue Nile Basin (UBNB). The study was based on 32 years Rain
 663gauge data (1987-2018) from 20 different rain-gauge stations over the 5 regions of the UBNB. The Rainfall Anomaly Index (RAI)
 664were calculated to identify dry and wet periods and based on its intensity, the years with extremely dry to dry and from extremely wet
 665to humid were observed over all regions of the basin during the study periods.

666 The precipitation variability over UBNB basin through tele connection via large-scale ocean atmospheric circulation were studied.
 667 Various wavelet methods are used to identify possible coherence features of monthly precipitation variability and their linkages with
 668 major climate anomalies (Niño4, IOD and ISMI) at different time-scales. It has been observed that ENSO, IOD, and ISMI influenced
 669 precipitation in various degrees at different parts of the UBNB. The partial wavelet coherence analysis also revealed that Niño4 is the
 670 most dominant index over Central Eastern and Northern parts of the basin while IOD is significant over the Southern and Western
 671 parts of the basin. Over all, ENSO is dominant driving factor for precipitation variability across the UBNB with the effective
 672 periodicity of 8-16 months while IOD at 4-8 months time scale during different study periods. The wavelet transform coherence
 673 (WTC) analysis on precipitation and ISMI implies a significant contribution of Indian monsoon to the variability of summer
 674 precipitation over the basin at 4-6 months periodicity via the modulation of ENSO and IOD. The spatial pattern of precipitation during
 675 ENSO and IOD events leads to the conclusion that the co-existing of El Niño and nIOD is associated with deficit rainfall while the La
 676 Niña and pIOD events leads to excess rainfall over the basin. In other words, a significant impact is evident on precipitation over
 677 UBNB basin when two or more oceanic index is co-occurred. The summary of the overall observed results was displayed on
 678 schematic diagram in Fig. 13. it can make a significant impact when two events occurred together. Fig. 13 represents a schematic
 679 diagram indicating the summary of observed IOD, ENSO, ISMI and Precipitation teleconnections.

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Fig. 13. Schematic diagram representing the teleconnections of IOD, ENSO and ISMI with precipitation over UBNB.

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